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Online Donation for Covid-19 as Connective Action in Indonesia and Vietnam

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Abstract

This study discusses how the internet facilitated the online donation movement to help deal with the Covid-19 in Indonesia and Vietnam. The internet has critical roles in online donations by spreading information, connecting individuals, and making an online donation movement. We use the connective action concept to explain how the social movement is developed by connecting people through the loose organizational or no-organizational platform. We find that the internet and social media have an essential role in informing, connecting, and simultaneously being a means of online donation activities of individuals from various backgrounds. In this action, individuals are connected emotionally and encourage their empathy and solidarity across identities. In other words, the online connection encourages people to gather and donate as social action. However, in contrast to the connective action concept based on real (offline) action, the online donation for Covid-19 shows that individuals are connected and act online. Therefore, conceptually, the online donation case could enrich the connective action concept in the context of online connection and online action.

Keywords: Covid-19, Online, Donation, Connective, Action

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 outbreak had not only health but also economic impacts. The government faces a dilemma between health and economic interest to deal with Covid-19. On the one hand, governments restrict individual movements to reduce the spread of Covid-19, but on the other hand, the policy had an effect by reducing economic transactions and resulted in decreases in productivity and public consumption. There is not only under government responsibility to handle this pandemic but also the responsibility of all parties. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes cooperation from all parties to overcome the crisis to face the Covid-19 pandemic. One of the contributions to help overcome this crisis is donating to fund health and economic programs and help people who suffer from the pandemic effect.

Since January 2020, the trend of humanitarian donations to help deal with the Covid-19 pandemic has increased. Governments, international organizations, non-governmental organizations, the private sector, and individuals participate in humanitarian donations against Covid-19. This donation had various programs, both related to health programs and other indirect assistance programs such as assistance to economically affected people due to the Covid-19 pandemic. One of the trends is the increase in donations made online, known as online or digital donations. The term online donation arises when people use internet facilities to donate to humanitarian aid programs initiated by the government, non-governmental organizations, the private sector, and individuals such as celebrities and community leaders. This online donation is a rational choice for donors, especially amid the Covid-19 pandemic, which requires them to carry out activities virtually and, as much as possible, avoids direct contact with other communities. A Fidelity Charitable reports that millennial groups are increasing their attention to making online donations during the Covid-19 pandemic (FidelityCharitable 2020). The internet is making donations easier through online transactions and protects donors not to make donations directly. In other words, the internet has an essential function as a means of disseminating information, connecting people, building public awareness, and mediating social activities in online donations.

Indonesia and Vietnam are two countries in the Southeast Asia region that experienced an increasing trend in online donations during the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2019, based on the Charities Aid Foundation report, Indonesia ranked 10th on the CAF World Giving Index (CAF 2019). The report shows that the Indonesian people are ranked second globally as people who like to do charity activities. The reports from several humanitarian aid distribution agencies in Indonesia- since the Indonesian government announced the first Covid-19 case in early March 2020-shows that there has been an increase in online donations on various aid platforms that have reached IDR 74 billion (Evandio 2020). Meanwhile, the increasing charity trend also happens in Vietnam. Most of the donations include an online donation, are managed by governmental institutions, and initiated by celebrities or community leaders to attract public attention to help alleviate the impact of Covid-19. In Indonesia and Vietnam, social media plays a vital role in sharing online donation information with the public. This article discusses online donation activities in Indonesia and Vietnam, using the concept of connective actions. In general, connective actions discuss an action formed by connections between individuals with different backgrounds and interests, but the same emotions unite them to act, both social and political (Bennet and Segerberg 2012). In contrast to collective action, which relies on an organization's role that facilitates relationships between individuals in action, connective action does not require a particular organization for mediation, but emotional relationships as the main force that connects individuals to take collective action. In other words, the action in the connective action is more fluid and flexible than the action in the collective action. This article explains the online donation activity related to Covid-19 as connective action in several sections. First, we describe the connective action concept by Bennet and Segeberg. Second, we describe the pattern of online donation related to Covid-19 in Indonesia and Vietnam. Third, we discuss online donation in Indonesia and Vietnam, and the fourth is the discussion of online donation as a connective action.

2. Connective Action

Collective action recognizes the essential role of the organization to organize and shape the action. The organization becomes a medium for forming common interests and creating a network of interests and goals. Meanwhile, connective action emphasizes actions that are not based on membership in an organization. In other words, the role of the organization in action is minimal or non-existent. Connective action explains social or political action in a society that seems unorganized in one large organization. The action participants are mediated by a shared emotion and connected by digital media, including social media. Digital media or social media is what evokes emotional relationships between participants in the action. Rather than being driven by the same principles, identities, and backgrounds associated with the organization in collective action, active participants in connective action are "linked" to shared emotions that can be followed by individuals with different identities, principles, and backgrounds, even they may not come from the same organization.

The fundamental difference between connective and collective action is in the origins of the action itself. Collective and connective actions have differences in their basic logic (Bennet and Segerberg 2012). Collective

action emphasizes the organization's role in forming a collective identity, organizing a network of relationships between individuals or members, and carrying out collective actions. Collective action based on this organization has challenges in the context of forming a shared identity (socialization or education), organizational costs, and the emergence of individual dilemma situations in the process of forming a shared identity or inaction. Meanwhile, connective action emphasizes digital media's role, facilitating the emergence of shared interests between individuals who are connected in loose social networks. In other words, digital media plays an organizational role in connective action.

In connective action, digital media facilitates communication and networks between individuals who may have different backgrounds. These individuals are connected, form interpersonal trust, shared belief, and solidarity, then participate in collective action (Caraway 2015; Heberer 2016; Ingrams 2017). Connective action forms interpersonal communication that rests on symbolic inclusiveness, a framework for action, and the use of technology that gives individuals the freedom to participate in action (Gromping and Sinpeng 2018). Digital media, especially social media, have two critical roles in connective action. The first is to build trust between individuals (Carson 2020), and the second is to facilitate content sharing between individuals (Carson and Vromen 2017). The existence of digital media also provides benefits by reducing costs and time in collecting and sharing information so that actions can be carried out quickly, easily, cheaply, and at the same time provide more extensive space for interaction between individuals (Cieslik et al. 2018). This interpersonal network in digital media allows the content to be shared widely and quickly to reach social effects. Therefore, digital media's role in connective action is crucial in "sharing" information and emotions through various channels, including social media. The power of this sharing can extend beyond national borders (Lim 2013). In other words, the function of "sharing" is the main factor of connective action where social media performs this sharing function in forming networks and relationships between individuals, spreading information, building solidarity, and forming collective action.

Bennet and Segerberg explain the differences between collective and connective action in three types. The first is collective action, where the organization plays an essential role as a coordination center for action, and digital media is used to shape and mobilize participants in the action. The second is connective action, where there is no or at least minimal role for the organization in managing the action. In other words, action networks are managed independently based on personal expressions shared on social networks in actions that are open to participants' access. The third is connective action in terms of the hybrid type. The hybrid type of connective action is a mix of collective and connective action. In this type, the organization provides a loose network. In other words, there are organizational actors, but their roles are not as significant as the first type as a coordination center, but only provide a means of sharing with personal action, unlike the second type, as the main force. This type's main characteristics are loose organizational relationships, technology, and action in the personal framework.

In practice, the connective action, in some cases, deals with more specific concepts. In the pan-European Stop-ACTA protest, Mercea and Funk proposed the concept of participatory coordination in connective action (Mercea and Funk 2014). According to them, the personal action frame, which is the essence of connective action, allows individuals who have different personal reasons to form common interests and form movements to make changes. In this movement, participatory coordination has an essential role in coordinating each individual's motivation to participate in the movements formed. In Downing Street e-petition, Wright argues that although it is based on connective action, the implementation of e-petition has a difference with connective action (Wright 2015). Wright saw the e-petition as more detailed and specific in their demand, and in spreading the message, the petitioner could not change the petitioner's actual text. Also, levubith's e-petition is linked to traditional media.

Meanwhile, in the #boycottautismspeak case, Parsloe and Holton proposed the concept of cyberactivism (Parsloe and Holton 2017). This concept is part of connective action, emphasizing the importance of the peer production process in a self-motivated sharing culture that makes individuals or participants distribute various forms of digital artifacts to address specific issues. Cyberactivism develops on social media platforms. Another concept related to connective action on social media is connective affordance. This concept discusses relational

relationships, which include the relationship between users and technology and the interdependence between users, and the potential effects of interdependence on technology use (Vaast et al. 2017). Social media has facilitated actors from different backgrounds to play interdependent roles and reach out to connective action.

The development of information technology, especially social media, has made connective action increasingly popular, especially among young people. In the Ukraine elections, the younger generation plays an active role in actions based on connective action (Doroshenko et al. 2018). Social media facilitates new types of political communication carried out by young people through broadcasts, new information, everyday political talks, and new political actions (Vromen, Xenos, and Loader 2015). Many young people are also actively voicing their opinions and forming collective identities through their various life stories, photos, memes, and other online artifacts through social media such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, and other social media platforms (Marchi and Clark 2018). From a journalistic point of view, Marchi and Clark call this group of youth action "connective journalism" because it builds and shares narratives about personal experiences and problems in the broader community on social media. Such information is not available in professional media. Marchi and Clark claim that in this case, connective journalism could be a precursor to connective action. Social media can also be the scene of connective action. Some activities that reflect connective-collective action on social media are formed online or in cyberspace. Other examples of connective action on social media are commenting, relaying information received, uploading materials and affiliating (Nekmat et al. 2015).

Connective action through social media does not only occur in democratic countries but also occurs in authoritarian countries. Feminist groups in China use connective action as a counter-censorship strategy when dealing with government restrictions on collective action (Zeng 2020). Meanwhile, in the case of the right to drive the women's movement, social media plays an essential role in shaping the online movement covering connective and collective action in Saudi Arabia (Khalil and Storie 2020). Collective and connective action complement each other, where Twitter and YouTube are used to expand campaigns, while WhatsApp and Telegram are used to build movement identities and plan collective action.

Several conditions influence the success of the action through the connective action. In practice, connective action needs to pay attention to the event's nature and how personal content in the crowd-sourced virtual protest can attract attention (Trevisan 2017). The case of disability group protests at elections in the United States shows that a controversial event such as an election can trigger mobilization but does not guarantee the success of the connective action to spread widely. The key to successful connective action is its internal coherence and personalizable action frames. The limitations of these two elements in connective action make it difficult for individuals to engage in action, problems with sustainability, and limited references to personal stories on the content of information shared. Criticism of connective action is also related to the limited explanation of the relationship between connective action with culture and ideology that causes action. Pond and Lewis respond to the critics by emphasizing the importance of understanding discourse as essential to form a network that ultimately results in connective action (Pond and Lewis 2017). Also, in implementing connective action, it is necessary to pay attention to the time to distribute the primary sources for connective action (Mercea and Funk 2014) as well as the critical role of characters or actors who have the charisma to influence emotions and mobilize support even though on the other hand this charismatic factor can be of short duration (Nils and Noomi 2017).

This article discusses Indonesia and Vietnam's online donation movement using the connective action concept, especially the hybrid connective action based on Bennet and Segerberg's typology. Online donation is a charity activity that uses internet technology. Internet technology has shifted the individual charity behavior from an offline way or donates in real, to a virtual or online way. The internet provides online platforms like websites, blogs, text messages, and social media to share and update donation information directly to the individual (Choi et al. 2018). The concept "online" here refers to the connection served, controlled, and operated by a computer network or telecommunication system, included the internet (<https://www.dictionary.com/browse/online?s=t>). The internet in online donation plays essential roles as the tool to share and update information and donate.

Online donation is used interchangeably with a digital donation to describe the donation activity on the internet and telecommunications, but we use the online donation concept in this article.

Hybrid connective action allows an organization that manages the action but not strictly and only acts as a network provider. Meanwhile, the formed network is determined by personal relationships and is not tied to the organization. In other words, there are potential roles for actors outside the organization, such as charismatic actors who influence emotions and mobilize participants in action. Online donations in Indonesia and Vietnam are usually managed by specific organizations that provide donation services. However, they do not strictly bind participants as members or part of these organizations but are more inclusive so that individuals from different backgrounds can participate. On the other hand, celebrities or famous people also play an essential role in fostering participants' emotions, who then mobilize the movement to make online donations. The following section discusses online patterns in Indonesia and Vietnam.

3. Method

This study is a qualitative research where data was collected from secondary data. The qualitative method uses non numerical data and non-statistical analysis (Lamont and Boduszynski 2020). We collected the data from journals, book, mass media and internet for the information about online donation in Indonesia and Vietnam. Then we were doing analyze to find the pattern of online donation for Covid-19 in Indonesia and Vietnam.

4. Result

4.1 Online Donation for Covid-19 in Indonesia

Handling the Covid-19 problem that crosses health, economic, and social issues require the community's role from various parties. Some Indonesians were then moved to donate movement to relieve the victims of Covid-19, including the people affected by it. The Indonesian people themselves are known to be fond of donating and humanitarian activities. The 2019 World Happiness Report states that 68.7% of Indonesians make money donations, and 38.8% of Indonesians are willing to volunteer (Helliwell, Layard, and Sachs 2019). Meanwhile, in October 2019, the Charities Aid Foundation, an international charity organization based in the United Kingdom, released a report on the World Giving Index 10th edition. This report results from interviews and surveys of 1.3 million individuals from various countries in the world for ten years about community charity's behavior in various countries. In this report, Indonesia ranks 10th on the CAF World Giving Index (CAF 2019). However, among the top 10 countries with the highest index, Indonesia is the only top 10 country to have improved over recent years. The report shows that 69% of Indonesians like to donate their money, and 40% of the population participate in the voluntary movement. In Indonesia's case, this report notes that Indonesia's achievements are also related to religious giving. Based on this report, the Indonesian people are considered to have high social awareness, including donation activities. This donation activity also increased when the Covid-19 outbreak hit Indonesia. One philanthropic institution reported that amid the Covid-19 pandemic, philanthropic donations from the Indonesian people increased by 122% compared to 2019 (Mulyawan 2020).

In Indonesia, several online donation platforms appeared on the internet before the Covid-19 outbreak. However, when the Covid-19 broke out in Indonesia, there was an increase in online donations from the Indonesian people, especially in April, when Indonesians entered the month of Ramadhan. Marketplace company, Tokopedia, recorded a 20 times increase in its online donation features in April 2020 (Evandi 2020). Several online donation platforms state that there has been an increase of between two and four times the number of community donations, which reached 74 billion in donations collected by the GoPay platform (Evandio 2020). Several online donation platforms focus on specific fields related to Covid-19 and use social media to campaign for their programs (Setiawan 2020). Financial application OY! in collaboration with three humanitarian agencies with further assistance. First, the National Zakat Agency (Basnaz) focuses on assistance to health workers and families in need using #BantuCegahCorona. Second, the Amanah Foundation focuses on helping families who have to carry out independent isolation and medical kit assistance to workers who have to work during a

pandemic, such as medical personnel, cleaners, security guards, and logistics workers. Amanah Foundation uses #FlattentheCurve to campaign for its donation program. Third, *Aksi Cepat Tanggap* uses the hashtag #BersamaLawanCorona to campaign for food aid programs.

The online donation process in Indonesia, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, is divided into two stages and involves several actors. However, previously, we confirmed that this online donation activity involved many actors and channels, and we only focused on online donations carried out by crowdfunding organizations that provide online donation platforms. We divide the online donation process into two stages: the idea and dissemination of online donation information and online donation actions. Meanwhile, the actors involved are actors who initiate and disseminate online donation information, online donation actors, and actors who coordinate online donation actions. In the first stage, the idea of online donation was raised and disseminated to the public. The institutions, companies, banks, organizations, mass media, crowdfunding organizations, or individuals who usually influence the public, such as artists or other public figures, could play roles in this process. They create an issue, idea, or activity like a charity concert to attract attention and concern by touching the public's emotional side by using social media to disseminate information or campaign for online donation programs. At the beginning of the Covid-19 case recorded in Indonesia in March 2020, public figures, NGOs, and the general public made 513 campaigns and raised 1.4 US dollars (Fachriansyah 2020). An Indonesian celebrity successfully invited the public through his Instagram account to donate to help fight Covid-19 and collect 4 billion rupiahs in just two days (Winarno 2020). Indonesian artists also play an active role in fundraising activities to help overcome the Covid-19 outbreak by conducting online campaigns or concerts. Didi Kempot, a Javanese pop singer, managed to collect 9 billion rupiahs online in one night (Simanjutak 2020). The information about this online donation can be received directly by individuals from information sources or through other individuals on their network of friends through their social media. At this stage, mobilizing individual support for online donation occurs, and social media plays a critical role in disseminating information and mobilizing action.

The second stage is an online donation by individuals. They take this action by transferring some money to social organizations and crowdfunding organizations. Crowdfunding institutions provide an online donation platform that makes it easier for individuals to make donations online by providing bank account numbers or collaborating with other applications such as e-money and e-pocket to donate without making bank transfers. We see that individuals from different backgrounds receive the same information about online donations and moved to carry out donation actions or activities together online. In this context, we see the connective action at work at this stage. These individuals move personally and independently to act or belong to a particular community or group and move together.

An example of Indonesia's online donation action is the crowdfunding platform Kitabisa.com (literally means WeCan). Kitabisa.com is a platform that provides two main features, namely facilitating donations and raising donations. The donations made cover many fields such as health, humanity, education, and other humanitarian fields. Alfatih Timur founded Kitabisa.com in 2013 as a social movement that aims to help people who want to create social projects. In 2014, this platform turned into an online donation platform, and in 2017 the Kitabisa's application was launched. In 2018, Kitabisa.com connected with 1 million people in Indonesia, with funds raised of 500 billion rupiahs by popularizing the #OrangBaik (good people). In 2019, they launched the Kitabisa Plus program, which focused on health assistance and routine donation programs that made it easier for individuals who wanted to donate online and regularly every month. In 2018, Kitabisa received the Padma Award from the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia for Orderly Reporting in the Implementation of Money or Goods Collection. As of May 2020, there were 3,850,333 people joined, with a total number of programs of 63,964. In campaigning and implementing its online donation program, Kitabisa collaborates with companies, government institutions, NGOs, Mass Media, Hospitals, and Public Figures.

In Covid-19, Kitabisa is one of the platforms often used and trusted by the Indonesian people to distribute online donations. Some of its partners, such as companies, government institutions, NGOs, Mass media, hospitals, and public figures, have created and campaigned for online donation programs to help deal with the Covid-19

pandemic. We can also have their informed programs via social media such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Tiktok, and LinkedIn. On April 13, 2021, Kitabisa's Instagram account has 3,048 posts, 757K followers, and 1,075 followings. Kitabisa's account on Facebook (@kitabisa.com) is liked by 277,104 users, while on Twitter (@kitabisa.com), Kitabisa is followed by 38,4K users, while Kitabisa's account on Youtube has been subscribed by 236K users. The use of various social media and the #OrangBaik and #SalingJaga makes it easier for Kitabisa to reach the wider community to inform and campaign for its online donation program.

Together with its partners, Kitabisa makes campaigns for an online donation program to fight Covid-19. Individuals in society with various backgrounds - whether related to organizations, government institutions, NGOs, and people who get information from mass media, hospitals, or fans from public figures - jointly carry out online donations through crowdfunding Kitabisa.

4.2 Online Donation for Covid-19 in Vietnam

At the beginning of the Covid-19 epidemic diseases, Vietnam was regarded as a highly vulnerable place of its long borderlines and extensive trade with China. Policy Responses of Vietnamese Government follows critical principles: The first is to control the epidemic, respond earlier as in January 2020, with strategy: preventing, finding, tracing, quarantining, widely testing; Participating of the whole political system, especially mobilization of local resources and military forces; Transparent, widely and on-time communication (Lâm and Thanh 2020). After three weeks of "social distancing" in April, Vietnam had no local transmission Covid-19 case within 99 days. Then Covid-19 outbreak in the Central Region since July 25, 2020; Danang has been locked down (Beech and Doan 2020). The situation is now under control. According to Dr. Vo Tri Thanh, the Vietnamese government's spirit that "Fighting the epidemic as fighting the enemy" is the most important factor for minimizing the impacts of Covid-19 and recovering the economy (Lâm and Thanh 2020). Besides, daliaresearch.com shows that Vietnam has the highest percentage of respondents who think that the government does the "right policy" in response to Covid-19 (VietnamNews 2020).

To deal with the problems under the context of Covid-19, it is necessary an effort from whole-of-society. Depending on the Vietnamese citizens' and organizations' specific conditions, they may implement direct help or online donation to overcome challenges, including online donations. At the end of March 2020, in Hanoi, the Ministry of Information and Communications, the Ministry of Health, representatives of the Central Committee of the Vietnam Fatherland Front, and the Vietnam Red Cross organized a launching ceremony of "the entire people support the prevention and control of COVID-19 epidemic". The launching ceremony was held online to 63 points bridge of provinces and cities nationwide (Vu 2020). Governmental institutions called for donations from individuals and organizations.

Contributions from individuals and organizations will be sent to the Central Committee of the Vietnamese Fatherland Front, one of the mass organizations. This program is a popular way of donating in Vietnam to coordinate the humanitarian portal with texting/message on the phone. In other words, sending the message on the phone follows the regulation of the donation movement. The formula of this program is "CV n," sent 1407. There are many times that citizens intend to donate; one n equals 20.000 Vietnam Dong (VND). For example, if an individual wants to donate 100.000 VND, they will use the text "CV 5" and send it to 1407. This donation program was conducted for 90 days, from March 19 to June 18, 2020. During three months of performance, the results increased significantly from 133 billion VND (on April 9) to 153 billion VND (on June 18, 2020) that come from mobile subscribers (Hà 2020; N.a 2020; Vu 2020).

The money reached from this program will use to support health cadres, people who directly joint in preventing and fighting against Covid-19 in the quarantine centers, victims of Covid-19 who is being treated in hospitals, medical facilities; people are isolated in medical facilities, community and people that directly impacted on Covid-19 (the disadvantage groups). The program got attention from individuals and widely supported in Vietnam. Mainly, they use and take advantage of telecommunications. The internet's role is to spread information because, without the internet, citizens may still donate to this movement. Actually, "the high level of

Internet penetration in the population has several important implications for virtual association in Vietnam," and social media has become a part of the daily life of many ordinary people (Thiem 2016).

Besides, in Vietnam, artists also play an essential role in propagating, inspiring, and fundraising activities to get over the Covid-19 difficulty by organizing various online concerts. At the beginning of the prevention and fight against the Covid-19 period, famous Vietnamese artists performed for audiences via social media from their homes to encourage the campaign "Happy at home" in the context of implementing a strictly social distancing policy. For instance, a "24 hours music marathon online" was organized at the end of March 2020 and continue hold by Vietnamese artists to perform with the interaction of netizens on social media. Through these online concerts, the public figures also call for their fans and community to express the responsibility and support to donating for the crowdfunding of Vietnamese Fatherland Front or for a specific account of the program's organizers to support vulnerable groups Covid-19 impacts negatively. Moreover, the Vietnam Women's Union and RSVP Joint Stock Company, an innovative company operating for the community's benefit, holds an online concert called "Stay Strong Vietnam" (*Kien Cuong Vietnam*) on April 25, 2020. This event aims to call for individuals, families, companies, and organizations to join hands with the Vietnamese Fatherland to support women directly involved in preventing and controlling the epidemic and helping people who are most severely affected by the Covid-19 epidemic.

The online music live show was officially spread on YouTube channel "RSVP Vietnam," social media Gazo, Lotus, and channel partners, with exciting songs and performances for the audience. Livestream by famous artists from their houses such as Diva Thanh Lam, Dong Nhi, Thao Trang, Si Thanh, Bao Tram Idol, Thinh Suy, Min, Ho Trung Dung, Erik, Miko Lan Trinh, Phuong Vy Idol, Trong Hieu, ISAAC, Miss Ngoc Han, Queen Thuy, Singer Phan Manh Quynh, MC Phuong Mai and other guests. Many songs aim to inspire and enhance awareness for citizens performed by these artists in this event. Taking the "Ghen Covy" (Jealous Coronavirus) song as an example, this is a typical Vietnamese song disseminating information about disease prevention and control to the people through music. After that, it became a social networking phenomenon that attracted young people to record videos to raise their vigilance. Then it was translated to the English version. It is one of the exciting songs that Billboard selected.

These events not only bring about valuable spirit, but they also aim to donate to the fight against Covid-19. For fundraising, audiences donate through ZaloPay or bank transfers before, during, and after the show. Firstly, for support via ZaloPay, participants open Zalo, scan the QR code or visit the link bit.ly/quyen-gop-zalopay-2 to support. For each amount of donation, ZaloPay donates correspondingly to the anti-epidemic fund. This amount will be sent to the Covid-19 epidemic prevention fund of the Vietnam Fatherland Front. The second way to donate is via bank transfer. During the time of 2.5 hours of broadcasting, the program received more than 450,000 live followers and reached more than 1.3 billion VND. The donation money will be used to support women who are directly involved in the fight against the epidemic, and women who are negatively affected by the Covid-19 epidemic, disadvantaged women groups (Hà 2020). Apart from the "Stay strong Vietnam" concert, famous artists also hold charity events called "Vietnam Revival," which they perform and are supported by online platforms, including social media. On May 30, 2020, the concert "Vietnam revival" (Hoa Nhạc hoi sinh) attracted up to 1.5 million followers on nearly ten broadcast channels, including the organizer's fan pages and youtube - Dep magazine and Vinaphone, TV channel MyTV, VTV3, Tiktok, and many other platforms. So far, the amount of money raised to the account of "Hoa Nhạc Hoi Sinh" is more than 353 million VND (Thịnh 2020).

Besides, "Coreference" is a series of online donations to promote people overcome challenges caused by a coronavirus. The initiators were all 9x young people. The leading spirit of Coreference is "Pay it Forward", help to share knowledge, the pervasive positive inspiration for the community, and this is a part of the effort to donate for activities to fight against Covid-19. Admin of this fan page is Hoang Duc Minh (30 years old), who established the foundation of charity donation Kindmate.net. This event attracted 1,400 participants. This program called participants to donate to prevent and fight against Covid-19 and share their Facebook account to spread with the community. Then, people continue to the other event on April 14, 2020, hosted by Nam Phuong,

a famous health coach. Donations are made through e-wallet Momo, coordinating with the Central Committee of Vietnamese Fatherland Front and Hanoi Medical University, used for supporting forces directly involved in the fight against epidemics (Thùy 2020).

On April 18 2020, Saigon children's charity, a British NGO and active in Vietnam, opened a virtual sports event register. Saigon children's charity holds a program called "The Virtual Steps Challenge." The program is a virtual race, where anyone may record their steps to donate for the disadvantaged kid in the context of Covid-19. The aim of this program is no kid left behind. Participants must register on irace.vn/races/the-virtual-steps-challenge with the free of charge is 250.000 VND per person to join this program. Players may select the aim from 50.000 to 300.000 steps to accomplish during four weeks of the race. For instance, all physical activities, running, going on foot, exercising, doing yoga, and housework, are also permitted to calculate these steps. When participants download the application Google Fit on the phone and access the account of iRace, mobile phones will be a tool to count steps (Tram 2020). The way to donate in this case is through the register's fee for players within the community. The way for the community to interact is through social media. On August 2, 2020, Vietnam Television coordinated with VitaDairy, a dairy company in Vietnam called support and protection for the medical practitioners. Netizens join the campaign by post the photo of the campaign on Twitter with the hashtag #Baovebacs24h or #VitaDairybaovebacs24h. VitaDairy will donate on behalf of netizens 10,000 VND to the 24h Doctor Protection Fund. The time to take part in this campaign is August 2-15, 2020. This fund will be used to buy Personal Protective Equipment for Healthcare Personnel. VitaDairy campaign has gained more than 600,000USD (more than 15 billion VND) (Dairybusiness 2020).

The online donations in Vietnam draw attention from individuals and organizations in the community to face and overcome challenges in the context of Covid-19. Calling for and supporting through online platforms plays an essential role in the charity, especially in social distancing. Although actors participating in calling for and supporting online donations are diverse, they may both individuals and organizations (for instance, famous artists, governmental institutions, NGOs, companies), they have a common interest and spirit that share a sense of community responsibility. Like in Indonesia, there is an organization that is organizing the donation, the Vietnamese Fatherland Front. However, other actors like celebrities and NGOs play essential roles in informing and create connective action for online donation.

Moreover, in some cases of the specific online donation called for by individuals or organizations, but the result/contributions from other individuals, groups would be sent to a specific public account of the organizers. These organizations or groups directly spent these funds themselves for specific disadvantaged groups (kids, women). In other words, they would not send money for these funds to the Vietnamese Fatherland Front (*e.g.*, "Vietnam Revival" concert, "The Virtual Steps Challenge" program).

5. Discussion

We try to explain the online donation activities in Indonesia and Vietnam against Covid-19 through the concept of connective action. Bennet and Segerberg (2012) explain that connective action is related to actions that are based on personal rather than organizational logic. Also, they mentioned that information technology provides facilities for interpersonal communication and a means of mobilizing action. The main difference between connective and collective action is in the organization of movements wherein collective action and the organization have a central role in organizing the action or movement. In contrast, in connective action, action or movement is organized personally, and there is no or minor organizational role. Even so, Bennet and Segerberg also provide a typology between these two forms of action, namely hybrids included in the connective action type, but there is still movement or action organization but not as strong as the collective action.

The online donation movement or action in Indonesia and Vietnam is part of the hybrid type's connective action. There is an organization that organizes this activity, namely a crowdfunding organization in Indonesia and Vietnam. Crowdfunding is a method to fund an idea or project by pooling money from many people (Clark 2011). Crowdfunding is an evolution from other concepts like microfinance, microlending, and peer-to-peer

lending. In the context of business, crowdfunding plays as the intermediary to fund the business and occurs as a new form of individual financing projects or ventures (Hemer 2011). With the development of the internet in the 1990s, crowdfunding grew to fund creative industries and then went to social projects. The crowdfunding in the social project, the charitable crowdfunding, encourages individuals from many potential funders to join online donation, usually for micro charity (Liu, Suh, and Wagner 2017). In other words, crowdfunding provides individuals from many backgrounds to fund social projects or programs by online donation.

According to Indonesia and Vietnam case, the crowdfunding institution has a dual role, namely initiating and campaigning for online donation programs to the public. Personal emotion is a crucial aspect that becomes the main target of connective action to get attention, empathy, solidarity, a feeling of the same fate or shared identity, and inspire them to take collective action. The success of online donations in the Covid-19 case is proof that connective action has succeeded in mobilizing individuals from various backgrounds to have solidarity to help deal with Covid-19. The Indonesia and Vietnam case also shows that social media has an essential role in disseminating information about online donations and becoming a forum for campaigning for this program. However, crowdfunding is not a single actor in this process because its partners also play essential roles in initiating, campaigning, and sharing information with the public. Although Kitabisa in Indonesia is a private organization and the Vietnamese Fatherland Front in Vietnam is a government-related organization, they play the same roles in coordinating online donations.

Even so, there are two issues related to online donation against Covid-19 as a connective action. First, the cases described by Bennett and Segerberg in Covid-19 are actual actions such as demonstrations or protest movements. Several other studies also use real action as an example of connective action. They do not emphasize the form of the action but the process of forming the action. In the case of online donation against Covid-19, the actions or movements that occur are not material actions but digitally or online. In this context, digital technology's role is to facilitate connections between individuals involved in connective action and facilitate actions resulting from the connective action itself. In other words, the connective action may create online action, the action in the digital world. Second, the organization's role in the hybrid type of connective action is to coordinate the connective action to assume that individuals who have different backgrounds may not be related to the organization's coordinated actions within the organization. Individuals are connected and act together. However, in the case of online donations against Covid-19, not all individuals are connected freely like illustrated. Crowdfunding is not the only actor coordinating movements or actions. Crowdfunding plays an essential role in the process of online donation. However, in the context of mobilizing support or participating in the action, other actors such as organizations, government institutions, mass media, NGOs, or public figures develop specific ideas related to online donations. In other words, ideas for action also emerged from these actors, and crowdfunding played a role in coordinating the action's implementation. In this context, two actors play in the connective action, namely the actor who has the idea of action- the actor who initiates or campaigns for the donation program - and the actor who coordinates the action. The roles of these two actors can be played by one actor or organization but can also be performed by different actors.

The contribution of online donation comes from mostly individual accounts (e.g., mobile phone number/ users, Facebook accounts, e-wallet, e-banking account). This movement may include the role of organizations that initiate, coordinate, co-operate, and call for other actors. However, if the organizations have not had the individuals' broad support, take advantage of media, information technology, whether their programs would be successful. In other words, organizations may call for donations, but their programs depend on whether communities or individuals are willing to pay for money, share, support, and donate for these campaigns/ programs or not. The online donation process for the Kitabisa case in Indonesia is relatively similar to the Vietnam case. Therefore, we suggest that organizations play an essential role in this movement, but we also emphasize individuals' role in online donation activity by taking advantage of media, information technology. In other words, the evidence supports the background theory, in particular, "hybrid-type," which is one of two types of connective action that Benet and Segerberg (2012) mention.

Connective action is a necessity in human relationships that are mediated by information technology. Information technology makes relationships between individuals closer and beyond boundaries of identity and background. Connective action allows individuals with different identities and backgrounds to connect, form emotions and solidarity, and ultimately act together. The case of online donation against Covid-19 in Indonesia and Vietnam shows that individuals from different identities and backgrounds connected, build empathy and solidarity to help victims of Covid-19. However, online donation as connective action is how the connection is formed, and action itself is performed online. Therefore, action in this concept needs to be expanded not only as actual actions such as protests, demonstrations, and other movements but also in an immaterial context both online and at an ideational level.

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